

DIFFERENCES OF WORD ORDER IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation. *Word order is the one of the most pivotal aspect of both English and Uzbek languages. The thesis will investigate the distinctions of them, find and point out shortcomings. It explores how these differences impact on the meaning and construction. In this phenomenon, it is aimed to deeply analyze the relevant theories and compare the grammar of both languages through examples.*

Key words: *word order, subject, declarative, object, interrogative, meaning*

Аннотация. *Порядок слов является одним из важнейших аспектов английского и узбекского языков. В диссертации будут исследованы различия между ними, найдены и указаны недостатки. В ней рассматривается, как эти различия влияют на значение и конструкцию. В этом явлении ставится цель глубоко проанализировать соответствующие теории и сравнить грамматику обоих языков с помощью примеров.*

Ключевые слова: *порядок слов, подлежащее, повествовательный, дополнение, вопросительный, значение.*

Анотасија. *So'z tartibi ingliz va o'zbek tillarining eng muhim jihatlaridan biridir. Dissertatsiyada ularning farqi o'rganiladi va kamchiliklar aniqlanadi. Bu farqlar ma'no va qurilishga qanday ta'sir qilishini o'rganadi. Ushbu hodisada tegishli nazariyalarni chuqur tahlil qilish va ikkala tilning grammatikasini misollar orqali solishtirish maqsad qilingan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *so'z tartibi, ega, darak, ikkinchi darajali gap bo'laklari, so'roq, ma'no.*

Grammar is one of the most significant aspect of learning a new language. Making sentence is very important during acquiring language. One of the most primary difference among languages is considered their word order. Because every language has their own unique sentence structure. Some new learners struggle to arrange words in the correct order because their native language disrupt, and it makes hard to adapt to the new structure.

English learners switch from one grammatical system to another even when they have to learn new structure patterns. Regardless of the new patterns they are learning, learners tend to construct sentences using the word order of their first languages. Such phenomenon is termed as language interference. In the case of Uzbek learners, their language interference phenomenon is they tend to end English sentences with a verb. Another phenomenon of language interference is native English users of the language when speaking Uzbek, they tend to have problems with the subject-verb-object SVO structures. Such language interference is a demonstration of the recognition of the cognitive syntactic structure of the English learners. In addition, the arrangement of words with a particular meaning is also a system in consideration of order, which a speaker may use to highlights their meaning or intent. For instance, a change in the subject or object of a sentence in English changes the word order to such a level that the sentence may lose meaning even when it is a correct grammatical sentence. In Silko's language, the communication

is such that the word order is more flexible for it to be a rich system of affixing. The explanation of such paradox is more about the development of a sensitivity of the contextual differences of the language structure.

Simple sentences come in four main types from the point of view of structure: declarative clauses, interrogative clauses, imperative clauses, and exclamatory clauses¹. Fortunately, in Uzbek language it is the same as English, they are divided into four types declarative (darak gap) interrogative (so'roq gap) imperative (buyruq gap) and exclamatory (istak gap).² The internal mechanics of these sentence forms vary greatly between the two languages, despite the comparable grouping. To differentiate between the four types, English mostly uses auxiliary verbs, verb inversion, and fixed syntactic places. For instance, it is structurally required that possessive and auxiliary verbs in interrogative statements in English be inverted ("Do you know?", "Are they coming?"). In contrast, Uzbek allows speakers greater flexibility in sentence structure by expressing interrogative meaning mainly through particles like -mi, -chi, and tone.

To preserve clarity, declarative statements in English must also follow the SVO order. Sentences that break this arrangement are typically grammatically incorrect or stylistically incorrect.

1. *Hang the boy, can't I never learn anything?*³
2. *Burgut uy poylaydimi? — hayron bo'ldi Abdulla.*⁴

Both sentences are interrogative and it is expressed by question marks, which are placed behind them. In these sentences, we can see precise distinction, since the sequence in English is formed by putting modal verb (can) namely part of participle before subject, while in Uzbek language it is a bit different, it is made by adding the morpheme **-mi** to the participle for developing an interrogative sentence.⁵ As in Uzbek language modal and auxiliary verbs do not exist.

*This thought broke her down, and she wandered away, with tears rolling down her cheeks*⁶

*Eshon buvam uchishni bilmas ekanlar, men o'rgatib qo'ydim ularga, keyin birgalashib uhdik*⁷

These sentences express the meaning of information. We can say that in English word order strictly follow only one rule subject-object-verb. However, in Uzbek language, it is typically subject-object-verb, and in some cases, it adheres to the rule of subject-verb-object which impacts on its interpretation.

Except for some techniques such as inversion for emphasis, the verb in English declarative sentences must always come after the possessor. This consistency is important because English does not have the extensive case-indicating system of the Uzbek language. Word order in English is very important to grammar because it shows who is doing the action and who is receiving it. Changing the order can lead to a completely new interpretation or a momentary ambiguity.

¹ Swan M. Practical English usage 4th ed. "Oxford University Press", 2016. b 215

² Erkaboyeva N. O'zbek tilidan ma'ruzalar to'plami. T.: "Yosh kuch", 2019. b 319

³ Twain M. The adventures of Tom Sawyer. "The American publishing company", 1884. p 4

⁴ Umarbekov O'. Odam bo'lish qiyin. T.: "Sharq", 2007. b 15

⁵ Irisqulov M.T. Tilshunoslikka kirish. T.: "Yangi asr avlodi", 2009. p 136

⁶ Twain M. The adventures of Tom Sawyer. "The American publishing company", 1884. p 121

⁷ Xudoyberdi T. Jannati odamlar. T.: "Yangi asr avlodi", 2018. p 78

In conclusion, both languages have clear contrasts in terms of word arrangement, because they have their own way to make sentence and express any meanings. These dissimilarities reflect the analytic and synthetic characteristics of these two languages, which of course influence conveyed meaning.

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